

Framing Informational Advantage in Robotic Multi-agent Security with Quantum Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—Quantum computing is anticipated to impact robotic multi-agent military systems. However, computational advantage remains unlikely at military scales in the near term, as it requires fault-tolerant quantum hardware. Instead, this paper advances the concept of informational advantage: quantum computing models may obtain information that classical models cannot feasibly access. To address this, we model, using a synalgebraic framework, a concrete military scenario involving jamming-spoofing attacks against robotic multi-agents. A quantum reinforcement learning algorithm is introduced to exploit adversarial multi-agent interactions. Preliminary results obtained from a gamified scenario indicate the plausibility of informational advantage in settings where classical approaches fail due to informational complexity rather than computational limitations. It concludes by outlining how data from realistic classical simulators and quantum hardware can be considered too.

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I. INFORMATIONAL ADVANTAGE BEYOND COMPUTATIONAL ADVANTAGE

Already in 2008, a NATO report [20] identified both the strategic potential and the operational challenges of *multi-robot systems* (MRS) in military contexts. Since then, progress in *robotic multi-agents* (RMA) has been substantial. Today, the military deployment and experimentation of autonomous vehicles is widespread [17]. More recently, a 2023 NATO report [19] emphasized advances in RMA aimed at enabling meaningful and reliable interactions between autonomous systems and human operators. Despite their different emphases, both reports converge on a central issue: the intrinsic complexity of military deployments of systems with many robots.

The hybrid nature of the interaction of robots has motivated the conceptual distinction between MRS and RMA (cf. [2]).

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While MRS primarily emphasize the physical embodiment, coordination, and control of robotic platforms, RMA focus on the virtual, algorithmic, and informational layers governing collective behavior. In practice, MRS corresponds to traditional robotic engineering concerns, whereas RMA address the design of learning, decision-making, and coordination algorithms operating over multiple robotic agents. In this sense, the NATO report [20] predominantly describes RMA, while the report [19] focuses on MRS. The RMA’s perspective, however, remains comparatively underexplored in military contexts, despite its central role in autonomy and cybersecurity.

Because the field of RMA is fundamentally algorithmic, recent research has increasingly considered quantum computing as a potential tool to handle their complexity [18]. The dominant narrative in this area is the pursuit of *computational quantum advantage* (CQA): the development of quantum algorithms that can efficiently solve problems believed to be intractable for classical computation. Shor’s algorithm, which enables polynomial-time prime factorization and thereby threatens widely deployed cryptographic protocols such as RSA, is the canonical example of CQA.

From a military perspective, however, CQA faces a critical limitation: it presupposes the availability of fault-tolerant quantum computers. While such systems may emerge in the 2030s, their availability at scales suitable for operational military use is unlikely before 2040 or later. Consequently, an exclusive attention to CQA risks deferring the strategic relevance of quantum computing for autonomous military systems.

In this paper, we advance an alternative and complementary notion, which we call *informational quantum advantage* (IQA). Rather than targeting computational speedups, IQA concerns the ability of quantum-based models to represent, extract, and structure information in ways that are infeasible for classical models under realistic resource constraints. In complex adversarial environments – where observability is partial, interactions are contextual, and the order of events matters – informational structure, rather than raw computational power, becomes the dominant bottleneck. Therefore, our IQA approach not only aim to bring practical application of

quantum computing for autonomous military systems in the near term (hopefully early on in the 2030s), but it also has the potential to open a new frontier of applicability which is not covered by the CQA perspective.

Our IQA perspective is inspired and supported by results in neuroscience [16], [11] and psychology [1], [14]. These quantum-inspired probabilistic models have demonstrated superior explanatory and predictive power for modeling decision-making, due to their contextuality and non-commutativity features. Importantly, such results do not posit the existence of macroscopic quantum physical processes, but instead rely on the mathematics of quantum probability as a modeling framework for informational phenomena that violate classical assumptions.

Moreover, recent developments in security of RMA reinforce the IQA's diagnosis. The Cyborg library [8], designed for the study of security in communication networks protected by multiagent systems, highlights that informational constraints, rather than computational limitations, constitute the primary challenge. In particular, the fourth Cyborg challenge required participants to use reinforcement learning (RL) to secure a network defended by autonomous agents (potentially robotic). Despite significant expertise and computational resources, no team succeeded using RL alone [7]. The limiting factor was not algorithmic sophistication, but the informational complexity of the environment, whose latent patterns proved too intricate to be effectively learned with classical RL alone.

Motivated by these observations, this paper investigates the hypothesis that IQA can be achieved in RMA through quantum reinforcement learning. In Section II, we formalize an RMA scenario adapted from Cyborg using a new mathematical framework we have developed, termed *synalgebra*. With *synalgebra*, we have the structural tools required to model informational relations beyond classical representations. In Section III, we introduce a quantum RL algorithm grounded in this framework. Section IV presents a gamified RMA scenario and preliminary empirical results indicating that the proposed approach plausibly exhibits informational quantum advantage. Finally, in Section V, we situate this work within a broader methodological program aimed at integrating data from realistic simulators and emerging quantum hardware, with the aim of enabling IQA for RMA in military applications.

II. INTERGRAPH REPRESENTATION OF ROBOTIC MULTIAGENT SYSTEMS

Robotic multi-agents (RMA) are composed of heterogeneous structures. Typically, they include robots with different specifications, such as sensors, actuators, controllers, and communication devices. These heterogeneous structures may also operate under distinct rules and pursue different objectives, which makes such systems modular as well. In addition, RMA exhibit multiple types of behaviors, often involving several groups within the same system, thereby enabling diverse forms of interactions. Consequently, RMA are inherently hierarchical too [25].

To represent this complex amalgam of features in an integrated manner, we propose *synalgebra*: a framework of hierarchical equations designed as a specification language for classical-quantum multi-agent computing.

From a *synalgebraic* standpoint, the heterogeneity, modularity, and hierarchy of RMA are intrinsically represented by intergraphs. An *intergraph* is a structure characterized by (a) multiple levels and (b) edges defined both within and across these levels. An *agent* is a level equipped with programmable input edges (*sensors*) and output edges (*actuators*). In particular, a *robot* is an agent whose sensors and actuators are parameterized by time and space.

To illustrate the *synalgebraic* approach to RMA, consider the scenario shown in Fig. 1, consisting of multiple robots, explicitly: five unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), two ground control stations (GCSs), six video receivers (VRs), one intrusion detection system (ID) associated with the GCSs, and two jamming and spoofing attackers (JSAs).

Fig. 1. RMA exemplar scenario

Synal is a specification language that implements *synalgebra*. It has expressiveness to represent all the features and dynamics of the scenario underlying Fig. 1. Indeed, the library RMAS written in *Synal* translates the Cyborg library to the context of the analysis of RMA security like the one in Fig. 1. The library RMAS has 3 types of *robots*: blue (a, b, c, d, e, i, j, k in Fig. 1), red (g, h in Fig. 1) and green (p, q, r, s, t, u, v in Fig. 1); its *environment* is a 2D grid (free space in Figure I); and it has two *teams* of agents (A, B in Fig. 1). The existence of different teams exemplifies the hierarchical aspect of RMAS, the different types of robots the modularity and the different objects (UAVs, GSC and IDs) to compound robots the heterogeneity.

The notion of intergraph is the *semantics* of *synalgebra*. It is a new concept introduced to provide meaning to the *synalgebraic* symbols. There is also a *syntax* of *synalgebra* based on the concept of *thesis*, which establish the rules to handle symbolic operations. A *thesis* is represented by

$$v[\Gamma \vdash \Delta]^\omega$$

where Γ are the *antecedents*, Δ are the *consequents* and v and ω are the *contexts*, respectively, the *false* and *true* ones. Antecedents, consequents and contexts are *morphisms* like

$$\sigma : \alpha$$

where σ is a *term* and α is a *type*. In this way, we can express things like that $a : UAV$ and $b : UAV$, which means that a is a UAV and b too, and can be proved like this:

$$\frac{[\vdash a : UAV]^{A:2D} \quad [\vdash b : UAV]^{A:2D}}{[\vdash (a, b) : UAV \wedge UAV]^{A:2D}} \wedge_R$$

The notation may look heavy at first glance, but there are concrete reasons for it. For instance, the following proof is invalid in synalgebra

$$\frac{[\vdash a : UAV]^{A:2D} \quad [\vdash c : UAV]^{B:2D}}{[\vdash (a, c) : UAV \wedge UAV]^{A,B:2D}} \wedge_R$$

While it is true that a is an *UAV* and c is an *UAV*, they are in the contexts A and B respectively, which are both members of the universe $2D$ of the scenario. This means that they are acting in two different parallel levels, and so cannot be put together. Instead, a valid proof should be like this

$$\frac{[\vdash a : UAV]^{A:2D} \quad [\vdash c : UAV]^{B:2D}}{[\vdash a \otimes c : UAV \odot UAV]^{A,B:2D}} \odot_R$$

The capability of expressing this kind of subtle, but essential, details makes synalgebra a formalism far beyond other type systems. To verify this, consider the terms (a, b) and $a \otimes c$. They instantiate the types $UAV \wedge UAV$ and $UAV \odot UAV$, respectively, in a way similar to what is done in usual Martin-Lof type theories [22]. However, in synalgebra the *terms* describe *computations* and the *types* express *informations*; we can handle informations over computations – something lacking in Martin-Lof type theory. Thus, the logical “and” information of two *UAV*s is $UAV \wedge UAV$, but the physical parallel “and” information of two *UAV*s is $UAV \odot UAV$. Such a distinction allows us to represent important practical situations in RMA. For instance, if a is replaced by a new UAV in Fig. 1, say f , with the same specifications of a , we can deduce the following – where the universe $2D$ is omitted to save space:

$$\frac{[\vdash 1_a f : a =_{UAV} f]^{A:2D} \quad \frac{[\vdash a : UAV]^{A:2D} \quad [\vdash c : UAV]^{B:2D}}{[\vdash a \otimes c : UAV \odot UAV]^{A,B:2D}} \odot_R}{[\vdash 1_a f \otimes c : UAV \odot UAV]^{A,B:2D}} =_R$$

This very simple proof expresses multiple informations about the scenario. From bottom up, it says, first, that f is acting in parallel to c . Second, it expresses that a was replaced by f in A as an *UAV*. Third, since it has been proved that a was running in parallel to c , which is in B , we have a justification for the action of f to be in parallel to c . The term $1_a f \otimes c$ tracks the computations realized and the type $UAV \odot UAV$ describes the pattern of information obtained.

Another essential features of synalgebra are the possibility of expressing, first, approximations and, second, false information. For instance, in Fig. 1 we know that i is a *GSC* but not an *UAV*. Therefore, we can conclude that i is not similar to a because a is an *UAV* – if they were similar, they should be of the same type, maybe with different configurations (perhaps different frames, propellers, or motors, etc), but *UAV*s anyway. This kind of reasoning can be easily formalized in synalgebra:

$$\frac{[\vdash a : UAV]^{A:2D} \quad [\vdash i : GSC]^{A:2D}}{[\vdash (a, i) : UAV \wedge GSC]^{A:2D}} \wedge_R \approx_L \frac{[\vdash i : UAV]^{A:2D}}{[0_a i : a \approx_{UAV} i]^{A:2D}} \approx_L$$

In the proof above, the morphism $i : UAV$ is on the left side of the entailment symbol \vdash , meaning it is a false information. Note also that we used the *left rule* \approx_L , differently from the *right rule* $=_R$ that were used in the previous proofs. This is due to the fact that synalgebra is based on the Gentzen sequent calculus. Indeed, it also can express dependent implicative morphisms $\sigma : \alpha^\lambda \rightarrow \beta$, disjunctive $\sigma : \alpha^\lambda \vee \beta$ and negative ones $\sigma : \neg \alpha^\lambda$. This ensures that synalgebra has the same expressiveness of classical higher-order logic (Cf. [21]). Moreover, the synalgebraic distinction between identity = and similarity \approx is made, respectively, via the notions of *axiomatic* and *postulative* proofs. A proof is *axiomatic* when its assumptions are *axioms*, neutral sentences that are always true, but it is *postulative* when its assumptions are *postulates*, facts that are taken to be either true or false. As far as we know, synalgebra is the first mathematical system that allows us to operate with identities and similarities, which is crucial for the simulations of quantum processes.

The combination of these synalgebraic features situates the library RMA in a position to frame all aspects of multi-robot systems, something which may require the power of quantum computations. Indeed, to represent the complexity of RMA interactions, the usual classical notion of *bit* as an idealized form of a “stopped coin” may be not enough – 0 is the *head* and 1 is the *tail*. For this reason, we propose to explore the concept of *quantum informational advantage* (IQA): The ability of quantum-based models to extract information in ways that are infeasible for classical models under realistic resource constraints. In [3], we realized that quantum systems have an intrinsic sensibility to contextual information, due to the non-commutativity of their logical operations. Since then we have been working to design a framework to represent this, which resulted in our synalgebraic approach to quantum computing.

In *quantum computing* [15], the unity of information is a sof of “spinning coin” called *qubit*. The *quantum head* is a complex vector $|0\rangle$ and the *quantum tail* is a complex vector $|1\rangle$. The fundamental assumption about these qubits is that they form an orthonormal bases for $\mathbb{C}^2 = \mathcal{Q}$, i.e., any vector $|\phi\rangle \in \mathcal{Q}$, which we call a *quantum state*, is such that

$$|\phi\rangle = a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle$$

for some $a, b \in \mathbb{C}$ satisfying $\sqrt{|a|^2 + |b|^2} = \sqrt{aa^* + bb^*} = 1$, where x^* is the complex conjugate of x .

If the define $|+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$ and $|-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$ as well as $|i\rangle = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$ and $|-i\rangle = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$, then these qubits form a basis for the *Bloch sphere* below:

In this picture, the measurement of a qubit $|\phi\rangle$ is the process of transforming it into a bit ϕ , to stop the spinning of the coin. The interpretation of qubits as spinning coins also provides intuition for why the measurements must be probabilistic: when we stop a spinning coin, sometimes we get heads, sometimes we get tails. Thus, synalgebra assumes

Fig. 2. Bloch sphere

that every quantum state $|\phi\rangle$ is indexed by its probability p of happening, i.e. $|\phi\rangle^p$, which implies that $|\phi\rangle$ is the case $p = 1$.

These remarks lead us to the conclusion that a measurement is made of a projector in the Bloch sphere axes, namely, X^\pm , Y^\pm and Z^\pm . For instance, Z^+ is the projector in the positive direction $|0\rangle$ and Z^- is the projector in the negative direction $|1\rangle$ of the z axis. In synalgebra their rules are like these:

$$\frac{[\vdash |0\rangle^p : Q]}{[\vdash 1_{Z^+}|0\rangle : Z^+|0\rangle^p =_Q |0\rangle^{paa^*}]} Z^+_R$$

$$\frac{[\vdash |1\rangle^q : Q]}{[\vdash 1_{Z^-}|1\rangle : Z^-|1\rangle^q =_Q |1\rangle^{qbb^*}]} Z^-_R$$

Following this interpretation, the physical properties that can be detected about quantum systems, called *observables* – like energy, position, momentum, etc –, are self-adjoint operators. They are operators whose associated eigenstates form an orthonormal basis for Q , which means they are linear sums of projectors. For instance, we can observe the position $\sigma_x = X^+ - X^-$ of a state along the x axis, $\sigma_y = Y^+ - Y^-$ of a state along y and $\sigma_z = Z^+ - Z^-$ of a state along z , because these *Pauli observables* have eigenvalues 1 and -1.

Besides, the computational form of the Schrödinger equation, in which the Planck constant is ignored, expresses that

$$i \frac{d}{dt} |\alpha(t)\rangle = H |\alpha(t)\rangle$$

where H is the energy observable of the quantum system Q . This implies that $|\alpha(t)\rangle = e^{-iH} |t_0\rangle$. Hence, the dynamics of quantum states is changed by unitary operator, i.e., rotations on the Bloch sphere generated by observables. Notably, the *Pauli rotations* R_x^θ , R_y^θ and R_z^θ are the anti-clock rotations with angle θ along the x , y and z axes. In synalgebra, the rules for rotations are like these:

$$\frac{[\vdash |0\rangle^p : Q]}{[\vdash 1_{R_x^\theta} : R_x^\theta |0\rangle^p =_Q \cos(\frac{\theta}{2})|0\rangle^p - i \sin(\frac{\theta}{2})|1\rangle^p]} R_{x,R}^\theta$$

$$\frac{[\vdash |1\rangle^p : Q]}{[\vdash 1_{R_x^\theta} : R_x^\theta |1\rangle^p =_Q \cos(\frac{\theta}{2})|1\rangle^p - i \sin(\frac{\theta}{2})|0\rangle^p]} R_{x,R}^\theta$$

Finally, to obtain a universal computational quantum model, we also need to be able to formulate controlled quantum operations. We denote the *controlled* version of an operator O by O^{O^i} , where i is the *controller*. Their rules are like these:

$$\frac{[\vdash |\alpha\rangle^{p,|0\rangle_i} : \zeta \odot \eta] \quad [\vdash |\alpha\rangle^{p,O^{O^i}|a\rangle_j} : \zeta \odot \eta]}{[\vdash |\alpha\rangle^p : \zeta \odot \eta]} O^o_R$$

$$\frac{[\vdash |\alpha\rangle^{p,|1\rangle_i} : \zeta \odot \eta] \quad [\vdash |\alpha\rangle^{p,O^{O^i}|a\rangle_j} : \zeta \odot \eta]}{[\vdash |\alpha\rangle^{p,O|a\rangle/O^{O^i}|a\rangle_j} : \zeta \odot \eta]} O^o_R$$

The rules displayed above are intended just to illustrate how synalgebra represent quantum operations; the explanation of their details requires a work in itself. Besides, it is important to note that quantum operators are linear. Thus, it is sufficient to define their actions on the basis of computation – the qubits $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ in the illustrated example.

Another important remark is that the meaning of the rules is formalized with intergraphs. For that, we use some notations. For example, \star_k is the measurement in the z basis at the node k of the intergraph \mathcal{A} that represent a quantum circuit. Thus, the *meaning* of \star at \mathcal{A} is given by

$$\mathcal{A}(\star)(a |\alpha\rangle^p) = Z^+ |\alpha\rangle^{a \cdot a^* \cdot p} \vee Z^- |\alpha\rangle^{a \cdot a^* \cdot p}$$

This is short description of the foundations of synalgebra. It is a reformulation of homotopy type theory [22], combined with ideas from De Domenico et al. [6] about multilevel networks and our previous work about logical modelling of quantum logic [3]. More details can be found in [5], [4].

III. MULTI-AGENT QUANTUM REINFORCEMENT INTERLEARNING

Usually, *reinforcement learning* (RL) is defined in terms of *Markov Decision Problems* (MDP). There is a set of states S , actions A , a stochastic transition function $P : S \times A \times S \rightarrow [0, 1]$, a reward function $r : S \times A \times S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and a discount factor $\alpha \in (0, 1]$. The problem is to find a policy function $\rho : S \rightarrow A$ that maximize the utility

$$U_\rho(s_i) = \mathbb{E}[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha^k r(s_{i+k}, \rho(s_{i+k}), s_{i+k+1})]$$

In this *Markovian interpretation*, as Sutton & Barto explain in [23], there is an *Agent* that, given the state s_t and its reward r_t , perform an action a_t , obtaining a new state s_{t+1} and reward r_{t+1} . Then, this process is iterated. The majority of the literature about quantum RL follows the Markovian interpretation. This is unfortunate because it requires classical control of the dynamics of the learning process. Notable examples are the use of quality tables (Q -tables) and neural networks (Cf. [26]). Since our aim is the informational quantum advantage (IQA), we need a different perspective: the learnt quantum circuit must contain all information necessary for the agent to choose the actions and, thus, determine the states of the system.

In [4], we proposed a synalgebraic perspective on quantum computing, which are going to be extend here to a *synalgebraic interpretation* of RL. It is a reformulation of an idea implicit in Russell-Norvig [24], in which they say that: “Reinforcement learning differs from ‘just solving an MDP’ because the agent is not *given* the MDP as a problem to solve; the agent is *in* the MDP. It may not know the transition model or the reward function, and it has to act in order to learn more.” They have

not formalized the distinction between “given the MDP” and “be in the MDP.” We do that below.

In the *synalgebraic interpretation*, a RL problem $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{L}}$ has *teams* \mathcal{T} , *behaviors* \mathcal{B} and *environments* \mathcal{E} such that:

- 1) Each agent $g \in \mathcal{T}$ performs an action a_i in \mathcal{B}_g for a state s_i in \mathcal{E} given by a policy relation $\rho : \mathcal{T}^g \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_g$ such that $\rho : g(r_i^s) \mapsto a_i$ for $r_i \in \mathbb{R}$ referred as the value of the action a_i .
- 2) Each action a_i in \mathcal{B}_g generates a state $s_i \in a^g$ for a menu $a^g \in \mathcal{B}_g$ given by a transition relation $\tau : \mathcal{B}^{a_i} \rightarrow \mathcal{E}_{a_i}$ dependent of a conditional probability measure $\mathcal{P}_g : a^g \times s^a \rightarrow [0, 1]$ in such a that $\tau : a_i \mapsto s_i$ if, and only if, $\rho : g(r_i^s) \mapsto a_i$ for some value r of a_i and $\mathcal{P}_g(s_i|a_i)$ are both defined. We write $\bar{\rho}$ when this condition holds.
- 3) Each agent $g \in \mathcal{T}$ perceives a state $s_i \in s^g$ for a context $s^g \in \mathcal{E}$ as a percept r_i^s given by a reward function $\mu : \mathcal{E}^{a_i} \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$ such that $\mu(s_i) = r_i^s$ in which $\tau : a_i \mapsto s_i$ for some action a_i .

This synalgebraic interpretation is more complicated than the regular one, because it represents reinforcement learnability in terms of Kant’s conception of agency [13]. According to Kant, we should understand the actions of an agent as a realm in itself, beyond the realm of agent’s subjectivity and the objectivity of the states in the world. From this perspective, multi-agent RL is visualized as the following diagram, which we name as *reinforcement interlearning*:

Interestingly, we can recover the fundamental *Bellman equation*

for reinforcement interlearning as well:

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_{\rho}^g(s_i) &= \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha^k r_{i+k+1}^s \mid \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k}^s))) = r_{i+k+1}^s \right] \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[u_s^{i+1} \mid \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k}^s))) = r_{i+k+1}^s \right] \\
 &+ \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha^k r_{i+k+1}^s \mid \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k}^s))) = r_{i+k+1}^s \right] \\
 &= \sum_k \mathcal{P}_g(r_{i+k+1}^s \mid \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k}^s))) = r_{i+k+1}^s) r_{i+k+1}^s \\
 &+ \alpha \left(\sum_k \left(\mathcal{P}_g(r_{i+k+1}^s \mid \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k}^s))) = r_{i+k+1}^s) \right) \right. \\
 &\left. \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha^k r_{i+k+2}^s \mid \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k}^s))) = r_{i+k+1}^s, \right. \right. \\
 &\left. \left. \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k+1}^s))) = r_{i+k+2}^s \right] \right) \\
 &= \sum_k \mathcal{P}_g(r_{i+k+1}^s \mid \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k}^s))) = r_{i+k+1}^s) (r_{i+k+1}^s \\
 &+ \alpha \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha^k r_{i+k+2}^s \mid \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k+1}^s))) = r_{i+k+2}^s \right]) \\
 &= \sum_k \mathcal{P}_g(r_{i+k+1}^s \mid \mu(\tau(\bar{\rho}(r_{i+k}^s))) = r_{i+k+1}^s) \\
 &\quad (r_{i+k+1}^s + \alpha U_{\rho}^g(r_{i+k+1}^s))
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that we have used the Markov property – we can omit previous events except the last $\mathcal{P}_g(s|a, b) = \mathcal{P}(s|a)$ – in the equation before the last one and index homogeneity in previous one – we can use probability marginalization over a successor index $i+1$. These conditions are required for Bellman equation, which, by its turn, provides a receipt for the calculation of the utility of a state: just define a policy function. For instance, given a policy relation $\rho : \mathcal{T}^g \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_g$, define

$$\rho^*(r_i^s) = \arg \max_{a_i} \{ r_{i+1}^s : \rho : a_i \mapsto s_i \}$$

By substituing ρ^* for $\bar{\rho}$ in the Bellman equation, we can recursively compute the sum

$$U_{\rho^*}^g(s_i) = \sum_{g \in \mathcal{T}} U_{\rho^*}^g(s_i)$$

The maximization of the sum $U^{\mathcal{T}}$ can, then, be consider as the aim of a reinforcement interlearning algorithm for a team \mathcal{T} . In the case of quantum systems, however, we need to be carefull, for they actions happen in parallel. Let say we have a team $\mathcal{T} = \{g_0, \dots, g_n\}$. Then, a RL problem $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{T}}$ for this team must have a representation

$$g_0 \otimes \dots \otimes g_n$$

of the interactions of the agents in $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{T}}$. This implies that changes in the parameters $\theta_0^g, \dots, \theta_k^g$ of an agent g may change the parameters $\theta_0^h, \dots, \theta_l^h$ of another agent h in $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{T}}$. Albeit a challenge, such a kind of sensibility to interactions is, exactly, what we aim to grasp with the quantum reinforcement interlearning. We are on the right track. To solve a $\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{T}}$, we propose an algorithm with three stages.

In the first stage, called *Formation*, we encode each agent $g \in \mathcal{T}$ with two quantum paths *Outcome* and *Activity* defined as the circuits that interpret the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} Outcome(g) &=_{\mathcal{R}_L} |0\rangle \triangleright H \triangleright R_x(\hat{\theta}_0^g) \triangleright R_y(\hat{\theta}_1^g) \triangleright R_z(\hat{\theta}_2^g) \triangleright \\ &\quad \dots \triangleright R_x(\hat{\theta}_{k-2}^g) \triangleright R_y(\hat{\theta}_{k-1}^g) \triangleright R_z(\hat{\theta}_k^g) \triangleright M \\ Activity(g) &=_{\mathcal{R}_L} |0\rangle \triangleright H \triangleright R_x(\hat{\xi}_0^g) \triangleright R_y(\hat{\xi}_1^g) \triangleright R_z(\hat{\xi}_2^g) \triangleright \\ &\quad \dots \triangleright R_x(\hat{\xi}_{l-2}^g) \triangleright R_y(\hat{\xi}_{l-1}^g) \triangleright R_z(\hat{\xi}_l^g) \triangleright M \end{aligned}$$

where $\theta_0^g, \dots, \theta_k^g, \xi_0^g, \dots, \xi_l^g$ form a partition of the parameters of agent g such that *Outcome* will encode the rewards and *Activity* the actions. The states are encoded with combinations of parameters in *Outcome* and *Activity*. If $l+1$ or $k+1$ is not a multiple of 3, we can repeat some parameters in order to preserve the pattern of the paths, without loss of generality.

In the second stage, called *Calibration*, we make the decoding of the *Formation* stage, obtaining the *reward* from the output $|outcome_g\rangle$ of *Outcome* and *action* from the output $|activity_g\rangle$ of *Activity* for each agent g in a given state, separated from the others agents in \mathcal{R}_T . For that, suppose that we have a dataset \mathcal{D} for training. Each $d \in \mathcal{D}$ is a triple $d = (d_{state}, d_{action}, d_{value})$. We will have that d_{value} is encoded in *Outcome*(g), d_{action} is encoded in *Activity*(g) and d_{state} is encoded in *Track*(g) for each agent $g \in \mathcal{T}$, where *Track*(g) is defined as the tensor of *Outcome* and *Activity* - details are displayed below. Hence, we define for $d \in \mathcal{D}$:

$$outcome_g(d) = \langle outcome_g(d_{value}) | \sigma_z | outcome_g(d_{value}) \rangle$$

and

$$activity_g(d) = \langle activity_g(d_{action}) | \sigma_z | activity_g(d_{action}) \rangle$$

Besides, we write $\min_{\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_r}^M(f)$ and $\max_{\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_r}^M(f)$ to denote, respectively, the processes of minimalization and maximization of the function f with respect to the parameters $\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_r$ using the Mealner-Near (M) method. In [4], we described how this can be implemented with synalgebra.

With all of that at hands, we end the *Calibration* stage by making, for each $g \in \mathcal{T}$ and $d \in \mathcal{D}$

$$\min_{M(\theta_0, \dots, \theta_r)} |outcome_g(d) - d_{value}|$$

and

$$\min_{M(\xi_0, \dots, \xi_r)} |activity_g(d) - d_{action}|$$

In the third stage, called *Optimization*, we first set

$$Outcome(g)[\theta'_0, \dots, \theta'_r] = \arg \max_{\theta_0, \dots, \theta_r} \{outcome_g(d_{action_0}), \dots, outcome_g(d_{action_k})\}$$

After that, for a team $\mathcal{T} = \{g_0, \dots, g_n\}$, we estipulate that $Track(g_i) = Outcome(g_i) \otimes Activity(g_i)$. Thus, we form the circuit for the formula

$$Track(g_0) \otimes \dots \otimes Track(g_n) : \mathcal{Q} \odot \dots \odot \mathcal{Q}$$

Finally, for each $d_{g_0, \dots, g_n} \in \mathcal{D}$, we encode d_{g_0, \dots, g_n} and do

$$\max_{M(\theta^{g_0}, \dots, \theta^{g_n})} \sum_{i=0}^n outcome_{g_i}(d_{g_i})$$

After that, we obtain the circuit $\mathcal{Q}_{\mathcal{R}_T} = Track(g_0) \otimes \dots \otimes Track(g_n)$ such that to solve \mathcal{R}_T we just encode its states in $\mathcal{Q}_{\mathcal{R}_T}$ and perform the actions that decode the outputs $outcome_{g_0}, \dots, outcome_{g_n}$ of $\mathcal{Q}_{\mathcal{R}_T}$.

IV. A GAMEFICATION WITH PRELIMINARY SIMULATIONS

We have been developing *Synal* as an specification language for synalgebra written in Rust with an interface in Python. In this way, we can explore the safety of Rust concurrent model and its integration with hardware description languages, on the one hand, and the usability and vast library support of Python. In particular, the library *RMA*, written in *Synal*, provides a robotic multi-agent framework for exploring quantum informational advantage (QIA).

At the present stage, *RMA* is far from been a full multipurpose operational systems for RMA, which is our aim. However, it already has sufficient expressivity to frame a gamefied version of the RMA scenario in Fig. 1, called *GameNetwork*. Below, we describe this gamefication and present preliminary data on a particular network topology. The simulations were conducted on a Dell desktop with an Intel Core i7-1355U CPU and 15 GiB of RAM.

GameNetwork has a grid with 7 rows and 10 colloms, as illustrated in Fig. 3. There are three types of players: Green, Blue, and Red. A Green player represents a video receiver (VR), a Blue may be either a robotic agent (RA) or a ground control station (GCS) or an intrusor detector (ID), a Red one stand for a jamming and spoofing attacker (JSA). The VRs are cells either in the 0 row or in the 6 row. The RAs are two contiguos cells either in the 1 row or in the 5 row. The JSAs are three contiguous cells either in 2 row or in the 4 row. The ID is five contiguous cells in the 3 row. Each VR has a *Position* method, whereas RAs, GCSs, JSAs and the ID has methods *Initial* and *Terminal*. These methods indicate the rows occupied by the agents. The *action rules* are the following:

- 1) Each round begins with all players in their cells.
- 2) The RAs and ID can move freely either to left or to right provided that they do not overlap with other players.
- 3) If C is a RA, R is a VR and $Intial(C) \leq Position(R) \leq Intial(C)$, then C can signal to R .
- 4) If R and S are VRs such that $Position(R) = Position(S) + 1$ and either $Intial(C) \leq Position(R) \leq Intial(C)$ or $Intial(C) \leq Position(S) \leq Intial(C)$ for some C which is a RA, then C can signal to R or S (maybe both).
- 5) Each RAs can signal to at most two VRs.
- 6) If K is a JSA, C is a RA and $Intial(K) \leq Terminal(C)$ or $Terminal(C) \leq Intial(K)$, then K can either jam or spoof C .
- 7) If D is the ID, C is a RA and $Intial(D) \leq Terminal(C)$ or $Terminal(C) \leq Intial(D)$, then D protects C .

- 8) If D is the ID , K is a JSA and $Intial(D) \leq Terminal(K)$ or $Terminal(K) \leq Intial(D)$, then D detects K .

Finally, the *reward rules* are these:

- 1) If R is a VR and C is a RA that signals to R and the ID protect C without no JSA jamming or spoofing C , then R returns a value 1.
- 2) If R is a VR and C is a RA that signals to R but a JSA jams C without the ID either protecting C or detecting the JSA , then R returns a value -2.
- 3) If R is a VR and C is a RA that signals to R but a JSA spoofs C without the ID either protecting C or detecting the JSA , then R returns a value -3.

The *Utility* of a round of GameNetwork is the sum of the values that the VR players return.

Fig. 3. Idealized game scenario

To apply the quantum reinforcement interlearning algorithm from the previous section to GameNetwork, we encode each VR player g as an $Outcome(g)$ and each player h which is either a RA or a GCS as an $Activity(h)$. The positions, values and actions are encoded with three parameters $\theta_0, \theta_1, \theta_2$ for each agent. We also add a qubit and a track with parameters ξ_0, ξ_1, ξ_2 to represent the JSA players.

Aiming to test the sensitivity of quantum reinforcement interlearning to the order that the operations are applied and, thus, observing some sort of IQA, we partition the GameNetwork scenario into two parts:

- 1) The part A has the rows from 0 to 3 (included).
- 2) The part B has the rows from 3 (included) to 6.

Therefore, the ID appears into both parts, A and B . This is the reason for the existence of two dashed arrows in Fig. 1 from the ID to A and B ; it protects both. In this way, we have a new *structural rule*:

- Either all of the RAs of the parts A and B make their moves and, after that, the ID can move.
- Or the ID makes its move first and, after that, the RAs of the parts A and B can make their moves.

To represent the fact that the ID is in the two different partitions A and B in a meaningful physical sense, we introduce a quantum teleportation. This is, exactly, the kind of IQA which potentially quantum computing models may provide.

The *teleport* operation defines a link between a node in a module and another module. The synalgebraic formula that describes teleport is this:

$$1_{A \triangleright B} \phi : A \triangleright B =_{\mathcal{LR}} [A \approx (|\alpha\rangle \triangleright \mathbb{1} \triangleright \mathbb{1}^\circ \triangleright \square \triangleright \star^\circ \triangleright |\rho\rangle) \otimes (|0\rangle \triangleright \square \triangleright \mathbb{1}^\circ \triangleright \diamond^{\circ 2} \triangleright \star^{\circ 3} \triangleright |\eta\rangle) \wedge [B \approx (|0\rangle \triangleright \mathbb{1} \triangleright \diamond^{\circ 2} \triangleright \diamond^{\circ 5} \triangleright \textcircled{\pi}^{\circ 6} \triangleright |\alpha\rangle)]$$

You can see its intergraph representation below – the synalgebraic version of its quantum gate quantum circuit:

Fig. 4. Teleport operation

Note that the teleport $A \triangleright B$ is just a conventional quantum teleportation protocol [10]. It relies on the creation of a Bell entangled state. The novelty here is that we can represent the computation of the circuit with the logical rules. We do not need any notion associated to matrices, as it is usual. This would make practically impossible to perform significant classical computational statistical analysis of complex quantum circuits like the ones for quantum reinforcement interlearning.

Given the $Q_{\mathcal{LR}}$ algorithm from the previous section and the GameNetwork from this one, we performed some initial simulations. Below Fig. 5 display data about runs with 20 000 episodes; one sample for each. Many sample were randomly reused to train the $Q_{\mathcal{LR}}$ circuit. Fig. 5 displays data about rounds with 5 up to 8 VRs in each part (A and B). This explains why the upper bound of the data is 16 utility. Besides, they have 2 JSA s and 2 GCS in each part too, and thus the low about around -30 utility. There are many possible combinations of the scenario. Fig. 5 illustrates the most complex. In future work, we will provide statistical analyses.

The blue data is generated in the scenario in which the structural rule permitted the RAs to move first, the red data represent the scenario in which the ID moved first. We performed a simple Mann-Whitney U Test that indicated with 95% of confidence level that there are significant differences in the results of both methods. As we can see, in the beginning

Fig. 5. Simulation data

both work similarly, but at around 10000 episodes, there is a bifurcation. Probably, because the movement of the RAs can cover the VRs more easily, since there are more degrees of freedom for movements.

We delegate, however, the justification for further works. We avoid drawing conclusions until more samples are collected and statistical analyses are performed. For now, we just intend to point out that there appear to be patterns worth investigating. This was precisely our aim: to demonstrate that the synalgebraic framework enables the possibility of informational quantum advantage (IQA), which appears to be the case – at least, the hypothesis was not rejected yet.

V. A METHODOLOGY FOR INFORMATIONAL QUANTUM ADVANTAGE

The data obtained from the gamified GameNetwork representation of the RMA scenario shown in Fig. 1 are promising. However, further studies and broader collaborations are required to consolidate the methodology underlying RMA and to achieve rigorous statistical validation through realistic experiments. In addition, an important next step is the integration of the synalgebraic framework developed here with empirical data obtained from real quantum hardware. Such integration would enable a more robust statistical validation of the proposed quantum reinforcement learning models.

On this basis, we propose a methodology for IQA structured around four distinct levels: gamification, simulation, emulation, and quantization. As illustrated below, the first two levels are virtual in the sense that they operate exclusively on synthetic data. In contrast, the emulation and quantization levels combine synthetic and empirical data.

This methodology is organized in terms of levels, not stages. Gamification, for example, is not a preparatory step that is superseded by subsequent analyses; rather, it provides a distinct and irreducible form of information. As demonstrated

in the design of the GameNetwork, gamification requires the explicit specification of rules. More complex games can reveal structural features of RMA behavior that may remain imperceptible in emulation-based approaches, where the underlying rules of the system are not fully accessible.

A further distinguishing feature of this methodology is its shift in emphasis from the accuracy of quantum computations to their precision. Achieving informational quantum advantage does not require fully fault-tolerant quantum computers. Instead, it suffices to employ sufficiently calibrated quantum devices capable of supporting meaningful statistical analyses. Recent work [9] has demonstrated practical techniques for improving the precision of near-term quantum hardware. The fact that both software and hardware components can be represented within the synalgebraic framework may provide valuable tools for systematically exploiting such advances.

While significant work remains, the approach presented in this paper offers a principled pathway toward IQA in RMA. We expect this idea can contribute to a deeper and operationally relevant quantum understanding of RMA in military applications. In [12], Kant asked: “What does nature do in relation to the end which man’s own reason prescribes to him as a duty, i.e. how does nature help to promote his moral purpose?” We believe it is upon to us to rationally determine human valid moral standards as well as to explore the quantumness of nature as a mean for the promotion of peace. That is the purpose of the concept of IQA.

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